

Managing Editor's Column

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Dear Readers:

This issue of J.UCS contains expanded versions of four award winning papers that will be presented at the WebNet'98 (<http://www.aace.org/conf/webnet>) conference in Orlando, Florida, at the beginning of November 1998. Thus, as readers of J.UCS, you have a first glimpse of some of the good work to be presented at the above mentioned conference.

I would also like to thank the authors for adapting their papers for J.UCS, and AACE (<http://www.aace.org/>), the organizer of WebNet, for the permission to publish the extended versions in J.UCS.

Happy reading!

Yours cordially,

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'H. Maurer', with a long horizontal flourish extending to the right.

Hermann Maurer
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